

365 →

files

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THE BRITISH INSTITUTE OF PERSIAN STUDIES

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تلفن : ۴۲۳۱۷
تهران

238, Ave. Takhte Jamshid.
Tel: 42317
Teheran
July 6, 1969

Andrew Williamson, Esq.
Ollaberry,
Grimms Hill,
Great Missenden,
Bucks.,
ENGLAND

Handwritten notes:
I need 40 rolls Kodachrome
5x20 of 35 mil.
120 B+W → 20 rolls.
Adox. 40 rolls of 35m 36 ~~expos.~~

Dear Andrew,

Our letters crossed in the post and I see that most of the points you raised I have already mentioned. Please try to work on Len Harrow. We will somehow manage to support him between us and I know from experience that he can be much more economical about things than I can, so that having him with me may even prove a saving.

Your suggestion of a lift to Marageh on your way to Turkey sounds good - I may take you up on it. The money does not seem overmuch. I will see what I can do to find ways to augment this either from any monies I can squeeze out of the Institute or from my own pocket if only my money starts coming through.

I must admit that on principle I don't heavily approve of girls on digs, particularly such a small one but as long as they are prepared to rough it the way everyone else will have to, I suppose that it could work out since neither of them seem to have anything to do with Islamic Studies. Are they contributing anything in the financial way? I leave all that to you. Of course I am looking forward very much to getting the slides back. I think that you should arrange to buy a large batch of Kadachrome II at the best possible price. You will probably also be able to get a reduction on some Verachrome 120 black and white which is good for my Yashika. We will also need a batch of black and white, we will need some Triple X for interiors and a lot of something else for exteriors. I am not too keen on Plus X and would prefer Adox if you can get this, and, in fact, if you can get a reasonable quantity of this, say 50 rolls of 35 mm. (36 exposures), I can always use it in Iran. In fact, I can always absorb almost any quantity of film. If, as I am sure will be the case, you are in financial difficulty about buying the film please ask my mother for the money to cover my share and I will send her a cheque to cover what is necessary. However, please contact her before the 18th of July as I said in

my last letter. Does the Nikon fit our Pentax equipment? Check on this before you swap.

This seems to be all. I will let you have all the Pir Bakran etc. information when you arrive. We all look forward to seeing you.

Yours sincerely,

Antony Hutt

AH:ss

P.S. Just received a letter from Jennip Scarce who seems quite nice, so I guess I will have to control my misogynistic feelings for the time of the dig. She talks about my coming back on the 15th Sept. but I rather fear that in fact it may have to be the 10th, but we will talk about that when you arrive.

If you hear of anybody leaving